

Efficient SDM-MIMO Stokes-Space Equalization

F. J. Vaquero Caballero^(1,2), A. Zanaty^(1,3), F. Pittalà⁽¹⁾, G. Goeger⁽¹⁾, Y. Ye⁽¹⁾,
I. Tafur Monroy⁽²⁾ and W. Rosenkranz⁽³⁾

⁽¹⁾ European Research Center, Huawei Technologies Duesseldorf GmbH, Riesstrasse 25, D-80992 Munich, Germany, fabio.pittalà@huawei.com; ⁽²⁾ Department of Photonics Engineering, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Ørstedes Plads, Build. 343, DK-2800, Lyngby, Denmark; ⁽³⁾ Chair for Communications, University of Kiel, Kaiserstraße 2, D-24143 Kiel, Germany.

Abstract We propose a novel frequency-domain 6x6 MIMO Stokes-space equalizer and compare its performance to a 6x6 MIMO LMS architecture. This method is suited to overcome DSP complexity and laser linewidth issues in SDM transmission systems.

Introduction

The increasing demand of data traffic is challenging the current single-mode coherent technologies, pushing the telecommunication industry and research towards higher-capacity and higher-complexity transmission systems.

Space-division multiplexing (SDM) has the potential to scale capacity cost efficiently. Current experiments¹ show that it is possible to excite multiple propagation modes over a few-mode-fiber (FMF), called mode-division multiplexing (MDM), resulting in parallel channels over a fiber. The excited modes suffer from not only single-mode signal impairments such as chromatic dispersion (CD) and polarization mode dispersion (PMD), but also from specific effects inherent to the MDM such as modal mixing (MM) or mode differential group delay (MDGD).

In single-mode coherent schemes, the compensation of PMD impairments is achieved by a relatively simple time-domain (TD) butterfly equalizer². In MDM over FMF, the equalization involves more complex multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) equalizers. Furthermore, MDM systems tend to have longer impulse response due to MDGD, resulting in an increase in the number of filter-taps. The equalization complexity can be reduced by the employment of frequency-domain (FD) equalizers at the expense of the convergence speed^{3,4}.

Recently a Stokes-space algorithm (SSA) has

been introduced⁵. The main advantages of SSA – faster convergence over the constant modulus algorithm (CMA) algorithm and its high laser linewidth resilience – has been proved in TD⁴.

In this paper, we propose a FD 6x6 MIMO SSA equalizer and compare its performance against that of a FD 6x6 MIMO LMS used in three-mode over FMF transmission systems.

Stokes-Space 2×2 MIMO Algorithm

The TD 2x2 MIMO SSA equalizer has a similar structure compared to the TD 2x2 MIMO LMS structure. Both consist of four filters $\mathbf{h}_{xx}^{(n)}$, $\mathbf{h}_{xy}^{(n)}$, $\mathbf{h}_{yx}^{(n)}$ and $\mathbf{h}_{yy}^{(n)}$ of length N which are multiplied by the input signals ($\mathbf{x}^{(n)}$ and $\mathbf{y}^{(n)}$) to obtain the equalized signals $x_o(n)$ and $y_o(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} x_o(n) &= \mathbf{x}^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{xx}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{xy}^{(n)}, \\ y_o(n) &= \mathbf{x}^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{yx}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{yy}^{(n)}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the four filter coefficients and the two input signals are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)} &= [h_{lm}^{(n)}(1), h_{lm}^{(n)}(2) \dots h_{lm}^{(n)}(N)]^T, l, m \in \{x, y\}, \\ \mathbf{x}^{(n)} &= [x_i(n), x_i(n-1), \dots, x_i(n-N+1)]^T, \\ \mathbf{y}^{(n)} &= [y_i(n), y_i(n-1), \dots, y_i(n-N+1)]^T. \end{aligned}$$

The main difference between LMS and SSA stems from the error function and their corresponding weight update. While LMS uses the Euclidean distance between the equalized signals and the expected ones ($\hat{x}(n)$ and $\hat{y}(n)$);

Fig. 1: FD 6x6 Stokes-Space Equalizer.

SSA employs the Euclidean distance of the received and expected signals expressed in the Stokes space ($\mathbf{S}_e(n)$ and $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}(n)$), respectively:

$$f_{LMS}(n) = |x_o(n) - \hat{x}(n)|^2 + |y_o(n) - \hat{y}(n)|^2, \quad (2)$$

$$f_{SSA}(n) = |\mathbf{S}_o(n) - \widehat{\mathbf{S}}(n)|^2, \quad (3)$$

The transformation into the Stokes space and the error coefficients C_1 and C_2 are⁵:

$$\begin{cases} S_1 = |x(n)|^2 - |y(n)|^2, \\ S_2 = 2\Re\{x(n)y^*(n)\}, \\ S_3 = 2\Im\{x(n)y^*(n)\}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$C_1(n) = a(n)x_o(n) + b(n)y_o(n), \quad (5)$$

$$C_2(n) = b^*(n)x_o(n) - a(n)y_o(n),$$

$$a(n) = 4(S_{1o}(n) - \widehat{S}_1(n)),$$

$$b(n) = 4(S_{2o}(n) - \widehat{S}_2) + 4jS_{3o}(n) - \widehat{S}_3(n),$$

Finally, the filter update takes place, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n+1)} &= \mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)} - \mu \nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}), \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}) &= C_p(n) (\mathbf{m}^{(n)})^*, \\ p &= \begin{cases} 1, & l = x \\ 2, & l = y \end{cases}, \quad l, m \in \{x, y\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Stokes-Space 6×6 MIMO Algorithm

The generalization to three-mode over FMF system results in $v = \{1,2,3\}$ input signals: $x_{v,i}$, $y_{v,i}$; and output signals: $x_{v,o}$ and $y_{v,o}$ given by:

$$x_{v,o}(n) = \sum_{j=1}^3 \mathbf{x}_j^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{x_v x_j}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}_j^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{x_v y_j}^{(n)}, \quad (7)$$

$$y_{v,o}(n) = \sum_{j=1}^3 \mathbf{x}_j^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{y_v x_j}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}_j^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{y_v y_j}^{(n)},$$

where the thirty-six filters of length N performing equalization and the six input signals are as:

$$\mathbf{h}_{x_v x_u}^{(n)} = [h_{x_v x_u}^{(n)}(1), h_{x_v x_u}^{(n)}(2), \dots, h_{x_v x_u}^{(n)}(N)]^T,$$

$$\mathbf{x}_v^{(n)} = [x_{v,i}(n), x_{v,i}(n-1), \dots, x_{v,i}(n-N+1)]^T,$$

Others accordingly.

For $d = \{1,2,3\}$, the error function is computed in the Stokes space for each pair of signals (x_d, y_d) obtaining three pairs of coefficients (a_d, b_d) and three pairs of error coefficients (C_{1d}, C_{2d}):

$$C_{1d}(n) = a_d(n)x_{d,o}(n) + b_d(n)y_{d,o}(n), \quad (8)$$

$$C_{2d}(n) = b_d^*(n)x_{d,o}(n) - a_d(n)y_{d,o}(n).$$

The weight updates are as follows:

$$\mathbf{h}_{l_d m_f}^{(n+1)} = \mathbf{h}_{l_d m_f}^{(n)} - \mu \nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{l_d m_f}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}), \quad (9)$$

$$l, m \in \{x, y\},$$

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{l_d m_f}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}) = C_{p,d}(n) (\mathbf{m}_f^{(n)})^*,$$

$$p = \begin{cases} 1, & l = x \\ 2, & l = y \end{cases}, \quad f = \begin{cases} 1, & l = x \\ 2, & l = y \end{cases}.$$

FD Equalizer Implementation

The main advantage of the FD equalization over TD equalization is the reduction of computational complexity at the expense of convergence speed³. Convolutions (1) and (7) can be converted into multiplications in FD.

Since the difference between SSA and LMS equalization is rooted in the space where the error is computed, both algorithms are suitable for FD implementations. FD algorithm decreases substantially the complexity in MIMO systems with large number of taps^{3,4}, which applies for MDM over FMFs¹.

The algorithm implemented is based on the 50% overlap-save approach (Fig. 1). Considering 2 samples per symbol (Sa/S) input signals, each blocks of $2N$ samples consists of two concatenated data streams of N samples (B1 and B2) being processed, and finally the initial part of the signal being discarded (B1).

Results

The evaluation is performed in a three-mode MDM transmission system where each mode consists of a 32Gbaud non-return-to-zero (NRZ) dual-polarization QPSK or 16QAM signals. The modulated optical signal is transmitted over an optical channel where we assume that the MM is random and equally distributed between all modes. This is clearly the worst MM and MDGD scenario which is intentionally chosen to test the robustness of the 6x6 MIMO equalizer. At the receiver side the optical signal is detected by three synchronized coherent receivers and digitized to 2 Sa/S. The obtained signal is processed by the 6x6 MIMO presented in the previous section, followed by carrier-phase estimation (CPE) performed employing the Viterbi&Viterbi algorithm⁶. The PSK partitioning approach⁷ is used to adapt the Viterbi&Viterbi algorithm to 16QAM.

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the evolution of BER as a function of the step size μ . In this case, apart from noise loading the optical channel consists of random state-of-polarization (SOP) rotation and random MM. Results show that, for both QPSK and 16QAM, the μ setting of the FD LMS is independent of the number of taps while FD SSA needs fine tuning of μ depending on the length of the equalizer. In fact, for FD SSA, the range of acceptable μ reduces toward smaller μ

values when the number of equalizer-taps increases.

By taking the optimum μ , as shown in Fig. 4, we observe no BER performance difference between the two considered algorithms, for both modulation formats after convergence.

In Fig. 5, we compare the BER performance for increasing MDGD values. Since the number of taps is equal, both FD LMS and FD SSA exhibit same MDGD tolerance. Despite it is not shown, same trend was confirmed for QPSK.

Fig. 2: BER versus step size (μ) for QPSK (OSNR=14 dB).

Fig. 3: BER versus step size (μ) for 16QAM (OSNR=21 dB).

Fig. 4: BER versus OSNR for QPSK and 16QAM.

Fig. 5: BER versus MDGD for 16QAM (OSNR = 21 dB).

Fig. 6 shows the laser linewidth tolerance of both considered equalizer structures. For simplicity only QPSK is shown but similar trend

is observed also for 16QAM. The proposed FD SSA algorithm shows a lower OSNR penalty compared to the FD LMS. In general, SSA is inherently resilient to phase noise as its cost function depends on the differential phase between polarizations instead of the absolute phase⁵. The OSNR penalty of the FD LMS is dependent on the number of taps of the equalizer. On the other hand, FD SSA algorithm is very resilient to the number of taps employed.

Fig. 6: OSNR penalty as a function of linewidth for QPSK.

Conclusions

We introduced a novel low-complexity FD 6x6 MIMO Stokes-space algorithm for FMF transmission systems. We observed no performance degradation in comparison to the widely used FD 6x6 MIMO LMS up to large MDGD values. In addition, the proposed equalizer shows high robustness to laser linewidth allowing the use of low-cost lasers in SDM coherent transmissions.

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